

masking agent. In presence of Hg^{2+} and Pd^{2+} , iodide solution was used for masking, and in presence of Al^{3+} and Mn^{2+} , solutions of fluoride and citrate respectively were used. Nickel if present must be removed by extraction in chloroform as nickel dimethylglyoximate prior to the estimation of zinc. The following foreign ions (I) caused no interference at I-Zn weight ratio: As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} and $V^{5+} > 200$; Pt^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and $Mn^{2+} \leq 100$; Zr^{4+} and $Bi^{3+} < 10$; $Mg^{2+} < 50$; Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and $Sn^{2+} < 5$; thio-sulphate, thiourea, fluoride, iodide, thiocyanate, citrate, oxalate, sulphate, phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, dichromate and sulphite ≥ 2000 ; bromide and tartrate < 50 . However, Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , CN^- and EDTA when present even in a very small amount interfere seriously.

TABLE 1 - DETERMINATION OF ZINC IN STANDARD SAMPLES*

Sample no. (Composition)	Zinc found %
Lead concentrates (42G) (Zn, 3.40; Cu, 0.14; Fe, 1.35; Pb, 75.6; S, 14.2; As, 0.32; Mn, 3.21; Sb, 0.15; Bi, 0.02; Ag, 0.074; Au, 0.016 %)	3.31
Gun-metal (6g) (Cu, 86.4; Zn, 1.30; Sn, 10.5; Pb, 1.02; Fe, 0.2; Ni, 0.26; P, 11 %)	1.34

*Obtained from B. A. S. Ltd., U. K.

Applications: The method was applied to determine zinc from standard samples. Dissolution of the samples was done following the standard procedure⁹. The results obtained from three determinations of each sample, are given in Table 1.

Precision and accuracy: A standard solution containing 5 μ g of zinc was estimated (10 times) by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.641 with a standard deviation of 0.007 absorbance unit and a relative error of $\pm 0.78\%$.

The present method is more sensitive than the dithizone method¹⁰ and the determination of zinc can be carried out in presence of most of the common ions. The total operation time in each run is 15-20 min.

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Chlorohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant in Aqueous Medium

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In continuation of our earlier work on halo-hydantoin as oxidimetric titrants¹⁻⁵, we introduce the sodium salt of 1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (which can be called 'chlorohydantoin') as a new oxidimetric titrant in aqueous medium. The results of determination of 22 reductants of diverse types using chlorohydantoin as the titrant are reported.

Experimental

Chlorohydantoin was prepared from dichlorohydantoin (DCH), which in turn, was prepared from 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as reported^{1,6}. DCH (5g) was added in small portions with stirring, to a hot 10% aqueous solution ($\sim 80^\circ$) of sodium hydroxide. When all the DCH dissolved, the solution was cooled in ice to get white crystals of chlorohydantoin, which were washed with ice-cold saturated solution of sodium chloride and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . The purity of the sample was checked by elemental analysis⁷ (Found: N, 15.6; Cl, 19.0. Requires: N 15.2; Cl, 19.2%). A 0.05M solution of chlorohydantoin was prepared in water. The solution was kept in an amber coloured bottle, and standardised daily iodometrically⁸.

Standard solutions ($\sim 0.1N$) of all reductants other than the two thiosemicarbazide complexes were prepared by the reported methods⁹. The two thiosemicarbazides of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} were prepared by the reported method⁷. Decinormal solutions of these complexes were prepared in 2N hydrochloric acid and the strengths checked by standard methods^{9,10}.

Procedures: For direct visual titration, a 1% solution of solid potassium iodide and 1% starch solution

NOTES

(2 ml) were added to a measured amount (10–20 ml) of the reductant solution. The solution was diluted to 100 ml with water and titrated with standard chlorohydantoin solution to a permanent blue colouration. For excess-back titrations, a known amount (10–20 ml) of the reductant solution and 2*N* hydrochloric acid (10 ml) were added to a measured portion (40 ml) of the standard chlorohydantoin solution. The reaction mixture was diluted to 100 ml with water and kept for 15–20 min. Then 10% potassium iodide solution (10 ml) was added to it and the iodine liberated was titrated with standard thiosulphate solution.

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATIONS USING CHLOROXYDANTOIN

Reductant	Range studied mmol	Standard deviation* μ mol	Average error %
Direct visual method			
Arsenic(III)	0.25–0.81	1.91	0.16
Antimony(III)	0.24–0.89	1.6	0.19
Tin(II)	0.14–0.40	1.79	0.15
Ascorbic acid	0.36–0.99	1.57	0.31
Hydroquinone	0.28–0.79	1.11	0.10
Excess-back method			
Mercury(I)	0.20–0.57	2.3	0.23
Iron(II)	0.19–0.96	2.55	0.18
Hexacyanoferrate(II)	0.14–0.64	2.42	0.21
Hydrazine	0.12–0.36	3.77	0.34
Isoniazid	0.02–0.26	2.72	0.21
Phenylhydrazine	0.06–0.24	2.67	0.26
Semicarbazide	0.07–0.20	2.68	0.24
Thioacetamide	0.01–0.08	1.53	0.17
Thiosulphate	0.02–0.13	2.73	0.25
Xanthate	0.01–0.06	2.49	0.18
Thiocyanate	0.04–0.33	1.98	0.16
Reinecke's salt	0.02–0.07	2.69	0.26
Hg[Co(CNS) ₄]	0.01–0.04	3.02	0.23
Hg[Zn(CNS) ₄]	0.01–0.04	2.67	0.15
Thiosemicarbazide	0.02–0.09	2.29	0.20
Zn(TSC) ₂	0.01–0.06	2.59	0.23
Cd(TSC) ₂	0.01–0.04	2.10	0.20

*Ten replicates.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) show that all the determinations are very accurate and precise. During the reaction, chlorohydantoin gets reduced to the hydantoin,

where, R = C₆H₄O₂. Out of the 22 reductants studied only As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Sn^{II}, ascorbic acid and hydroquinone were determined by direct titrations with the oxidant, while the others determined by excess-back titration method. A period of 15–20 min is required for the quantitative oxidation of these reductants. The reductants undergo the oxidation schemes as per equations (2–18).

In conformity with the oxidation schemes suggested (equations 2–18), one equivalent of oxidant is consumed per mole of Hg^I, Fe^{II} and hexacyanoferrate(II); 2 equivalents for As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Sn^{II}, ascorbic acid and hydroquinone; 4 equivalents for hydrazine, isoniazid, phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide; 6 equivalents for thiocyanate; 8 equivalents for thioacetamide and thiosulphate; 10 equivalents for thiosemicarbazide; 14 equivalents for xanthate; 20 equivalents for thiosemicarbazide complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}; 24 equivalents for Reinecke's salt, mercury(II)tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) and mercury(II)tetrathiocyanatozincate(II). The results indicate that chlorohydantoin is an useful oxidimetric titrant in aqueous medium.

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A New Spectrophotometric Determination of O, O-Diethyl o-p nitrophenyl thiophosphate (Parathion) Residues in Plant Materials and Soil

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PARATHION is one of the most widely used nonsystemic contact insecticide¹. Various instrumental methods²⁻⁴ are available in the literature for its determination. The present communication proposes a new method based on the reduction of nitro group of parathion to amino group⁵, which is subsequently diazotised and coupled with α -naphthol to form an azo dye in alkaline medium. The dye shows an absorbance maxima at 500 nm. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of parathion in various plant materials and soil.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol with 1 cm matched cell was used.

Reagent : A 1 mg ml⁻¹ of parathion in 50% ethanol and a 10 μ g ml⁻¹ solution as working standard were used. Zinc dust (A.R.) 5 M HCl, 0.25% aqueous solution of NaNO₂, 3% aqueous solution of sulphamic acid, 0.1 M aqueous solution of EDTA ; 0.2% aqueous solution of α -naphthol and 5 M NaOH solution were used.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 10–83 μ g of parathion were added zinc dust (1 g) and 5 M HCl (2 ml). The contents were boiled for 2 min, followed by gentle heating for 10 min. The mixture was then cooled and filtered and to it sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) was added and kept for 10 min with occasional shaking. During diazotisation the acidity was adjusted to 0.5–2 M HCl. α -Naphthol solution (2 ml) was then added followed by sulphamic acid (1 ml) and EDTA (1 ml) solutions. The solution was kept for 3 min and made alkaline with an excess of sodium hydroxide to produce an azo dye. The absorbance of the dye was measured at 500 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

A time 10 min each for reduction and diazotisation and 3 min for coupling were required. A temperature 15–30° was most suitable for complete diazotisation and coupling. Full colour development occurred at or above pH 11. Reagent concentration of 1 g of zinc and 2 ml of 5 M HCl

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PARATHION IN VARIOUS PLANT MATERIALS AND SOIL*

Sample*	Parathion originally found (μ g)		Parathion added (μ g)	Total parathion found (μ g) **by		Difference (μ g) in		Recovery %	
	(A)	(B)		(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
Tomato	23	20	20	43.5	39.0	20.5	19.0	102.5	95.0
	30	30	30	60.5	57.0	30.5	27.0	101.6	90.0
	21	20	20	40.5	37.5	19.5	17.5	97.5	87.5
Cauliflower	57	53	50	107.0	101.0	50.0	48.0	100.0	96.0
	55	52	50	101.0	99.0	46.0	44.0	92.0	88.0
	51	50	50	100.0	98.0	45.0	43.0	90.0	86.0
Cabbage	43	42	40	83.5	80.5	40.5	38.5	101.2	95.5
	45	43	40	85.0	77.4	40.0	34.4	100.0	86.0
	41	40	40	79.5	74.0	38.5	34.0	95.5	85.0
Runner beans	10	8	10	19.1	16.7	9.10	8.7	91.0	87.0
	12	11	10	21.9	19.5	9.90	8.5	99.0	85.0
	—	—	10	9.25	8.55	9.25	8.55	92.5	85.5
Spinach (different varieties)	—	—	10	9.10	8.75	9.10	8.75	91.0	87.5
	5	3	10	14.65	12.00	9.65	9.00	96.5	90.0
	7	4	10	16.58	12.40	9.58	8.4	95.8	84.0
Soil	44	40	40	81.48	75.2	37.48	35.2	93.7	88.0
	—	—	40	37.6	35.0	37.60	35.0	94.0	87.5
	18	15	20	36.9	32.3	18.90	17.3	94.5	86.5

* (A) = Proposed method, (B) = Buckley method (Ref. 4); Three sets of experiments done for each sample; Amount of sample = 25 g. ** Mean of three replicate analyses.